

Figure 3a: the 5x5 vāstu, BK vy 137-141, MY y+5c-y+8b.

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1 Brahmā and earth

5 Sadāśiva and ether

2 Viṣṇu and water

6 Indra

7 Yama

3 Īśa and air

8 Varuṇa

9 Kubera

4 Rudra and fire